

Synthesis, characterization and optical properties of nitrogen-doped ZnTiO₃

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Abstract : Nitrogen doped ternary metal oxide ZnTiO₃ was synthesized by organic precursor method. Metal benzoate dihydrazinate complexes were prepared by a simple *in situ* chemical method. The formed metal benzoate dihydrazinate complexes were decomposed at different temperatures to yield the corresponding metal oxides. The samples were characterized by FT-IR, TGA and DSC, powder XRD, DRS, SEM and EDAX. Thermal analysis (TGA and DSC) revealed the decomposition path of the metal benzoate dihydrazinate complexes. XRD analysis confirms the polycrystalline nature of samples with pure phase formation. SEM analysis shows that the formed metal oxide powders are spherical particles. EDX confirmed the presence of 7.5 wt.% of nitrogen in the cubic phase ZnTiO₃. The optical studies were carried by recording diffuse reflectance spectra. Using Tauc's relation $(\alpha h\nu)^n = A(h\nu - E_g)$ optical bandgap for nitrogen doped ZnTiO₃ was found to be 3.91 eV.

Keywords : Zinc titanate, phase transitions, bandgap, diffuse reflectance spectroscopy.

Introduction

Semiconducting metal oxides like ZnO, TiO₂ and zinc titanates have many interesting properties in with wide range of applications in different areas. ZnO and TiO₂ are n-type semiconducting materials with a wide bandgap of 3.2 and 3.3 eV respectively¹⁻³. Zinc titanate system is an interesting ternary metal oxide system with wide bandgap ranging from 3.6 to 3.9 eV and different polymorphs at different temperatures, like cubic Zn₂Ti₃O₈, cubic ZnTiO₃, hexagonal ZnTiO₃ and cubic Zn₂TiO₄⁴. Several methods were adopted for zinc titanate synthesis. Solid state methods require high temperature calcination for phase formation⁵. In order to reduce the calcination temperature, low temperature methods like modified sol-gel methods, stearic acid gel method and Pechini process were employed⁶⁻⁸. In organic precursor synthesis binary metal oxides like ZnO, MnO₂, Fe₂O₃, Co₃O₄, MgO, NiO were produced by decomposing their respective hydrazine or bis(hydrazine) metal carboxylate complexes at lower temperature⁹⁻¹¹. In this paper we discuss the synthesis, characterization and optical properties of ternary metal oxide ZnTiO₃ by the thermal decomposition of organic precursors.

Experimental

Zinc nitrate hexahydrate ($\geq 99.0\%$ Sigma-Aldrich), titanium(IV) isobutoxide (97% Sigma-Aldrich), benzoic acid ($\geq 99\%$, Sigma-Aldrich), hydrazine hydrate (reagent grade 50-60%, Sigma-Aldrich) and ethanol (AR 99.9%, Jiangsu Huaxi International) were used for synthesis.

Hydrazinium benzoate complex was prepared in aqueous solution by the procedure given by Kuppusamy *et al.*¹⁰. Zinc nitrate hexahydrate and titanium(IV) butoxide in 1 : 1 mole ratio were dissolved in ethanol and stirred at room temperature for 2 h to form a clear solution. To this solution hydrazinium benzoate complex was added with constant stirring at room temperature. 1 : 2 mole ratio of metal ions source to hydrazinium benzoate was maintained throughout the synthesis. White precipitate formed immediately. They were slightly heated at around 80 °C till volume reduced to one third of the initial volume. The precipitate was cooled to room temperature, filtered, washed several times with distilled water and dried. Thus formed precursor complex was decomposed at 450 °C and calcined at higher temperatures to form ZnTiO₃.

Thermal analysis was carried out using SDTQ600V20.9

instrument in nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 4 °C/min. Phase purity of the products was determined by powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) using BRUKER D8 Advance X-ray diffractometer. FT-IR spectra were taken with Shimadzu. UV-Vis spectra were recorded in the diffuse reflectance mode (R) on a JASCO UV Vis NIR V-670 using BaSO₄ as the reference sample. Morphology of the samples was investigated with HRSEM FE 1 In-spect F50.

Results and discussion

DSC-TGA graph of the zinc titanate precursor complex was shown in the Fig. 1. The weight loss of the precursor occurred in three steps in the temperature ranges 30 °C to 220 °C, 220 °C to 310 °C and 310 °C to 440 °C. After 440 °C no appreciable weight loss was observed. An endotherm was observed at 60 °C due to the loss of residual water. Three exothermic peaks were observed at 350 °C, 420 °C and 460 °C. It may be due to the combustion of organic compounds, formation of amorphous zinc titanate and their crystallization respectively. Above 400 °C there was no significant weight loss, indicating that organic compounds were completely decomposed to form ZnTiO₃.

Fig. 1. DSC-TGA plot of the zinc titanate precursor complex.

Powder XRD pattern of the zinc titanate organic precursors calcined at different temperatures were shown in Fig. 2.

The average crystallite size (D) was estimated from the Debye-Scherrer's equation¹² : $D = 0.9\lambda/\beta \cos \theta$, where λ represents the wavelength of the X-ray radi-

Fig. 2. XRD pattern of the zinc titanate precursor complex calcined at (a) 450 °C, (b) 550 °C, (c) 700 °C, (d) 950 °C and (e) 1000 °C for 2 h each.

tion, β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the diffraction peak (in radians) and θ is the scattering angle. The percentage of hexagonal ilmenite phase relative to the cubic ZnTiO₃ phase (H/C), was calculated based on the following equation : $H/C = I_{H(104)}/I_{C(311)} + I_{H(104)}$, where $I_{H(104)}$ is the intensity of the major peak (104) of the hexagonal ilmenite ZnTiO₃ and $I_{C(311)}$ is the intensity of the major peak (311) of the cubic ZnTiO₃¹³. Wurtzite ZnO (JCPDS No. 36-1451) and anatase TiO₂ (JCPDS No. 21-1272) were formed on decomposing their respective organic precursors at 450 °C. Anatase TiO₂ transformed into rutile TiO₂ on further calcination at 700 °C. Zn₂Ti₃O₈ (JCPDS No. 13-0471) along with traces of ZnO was observed in 450 °C calcined samples. Crystalline phase cubic ZnTiO₃ (JCPDS No. 39-0190) was formed on calcination at 550 °C and its crystallinity increased till 700 °C. Crystallite size calculated using Scherrer formula was found to be 60 nm. At 950 °C a mixture of 82.4% cubic ZnTiO₃ (JCPDS No. 39-0190), crystallite size 105 nm and 17.6% hexagonal ZnTiO₃ (JCPDS No. 14-0033), crystallite size 115 nm were observed. On further calcination at 1000 °C both the cubic ZnTiO₃ and hexagonal ilmenite ZnTiO₃ were decomposed to cubic Zn₂TiO₄ (JCPDS No. 73-0578), crystallite size 155 nm and rutile TiO₂ (JCPDS No. 21-1276). It is observed that nitrogen doping is not influencing the phase transition characters of ZnO, TiO₂ and zinc titanates^{3,14}.

The characteristic frequencies of carboxylate groups, N-H, N-N stretching frequencies of the hydrazinate com-

plexes were completely absent in the samples calcined at 450 °C and higher temperatures. It shows that the precursors were thermally decomposed completely to form corresponding metal oxides ZnO, TiO₂ and zinc titanates as evidenced from the M-O stretching frequencies observed in the range of 400–700 cm⁻¹ 6,15.

The bandgap energies were calculated according to Tauc's relation $(\alpha h\nu)^n = A(h\nu - E_g)^1$ are shown in the Fig. 3 inset. The diffuse reflectance spectra of the samples treated at 450 °C essentially differ from samples treated

Fig. 3. DRS spectra of the samples calcined at different temperatures.

at 700 °C with enhanced absorption. Nitrogen doped TiO₂ showed enhanced absorption in the visible light range of 400–500 nm. Generation of intra band localized states between valence band to conduction band¹⁶ and increased number of oxygen vacancies and defects may lead to enhanced absorption in the visible light region¹⁷. Li *et al.*¹⁸ proposed that the intensity of visible light absorption is directly proportional to the amount of nitrogen doping. The bandgap of nitrogen doped TiO₂ calcined at 450 °C and 700 °C was found to be 3.65 eV and 3.50 eV respectively. Nitrogen doped ZnO showed absorption edge near 380 nm. Substitution of N for O resulted in absorption of light of longer wavelength and bandgap narrowing by shifting the band edge upward caused enhanced absorption in the visible range for nitrogen doped ZnO. The bandgap of nitrogen doped ZnO was found to decrease from 3.23 eV to 3.21 eV with increase in calcination temperature from 450 °C to 700 °C, which is less than undoped ZnO 3.3 eV. Ashok Rao *et al.*¹⁹ has proposed

Fig. 4. SEM and EDX pattern of zinc titanates (ZT2) calcined at 700 °C/2 h.

that nitrogen doped ZnO contain higher oxygen vacancies or defects, less electron-hole recombination and narrow bandgap than the undoped ZnO. Nitrogen doped ZnTiO₃ showed a strong absorption in the visible light range from 380–500 nm. For undoped zinc titanates the optical bandgap varies from 3.93 to 3.60 eV^{20–22}. The optical bandgap of nitrogen doped ZnTiO₃ calcined at 450 °C and 700 °C was found to be 3.93 eV and 3.80 eV respectively. The increased absorption in the visible light range can be attributed to the doping of nitrogen in ZnTiO₃.

From the scanning microscopic images the synthesized metal oxides were found to be spherical in shape and agglomerated. EDX analysis shows that 7.5 wt.% nitrogen was present in ZnTiO₃ calcined at 700 °C.

Conclusion

Nitrogen doped ZnO, TiO₂ and ZnTiO₃ were synthesized by the decomposition of metal benzoate dihydrazinate organic precursors. Nitrogen doping enhanced the optical absorption properties in the visible region. The bandgap decreased with increase in calcination temperature due to the increase in crystallite size on calcination and nitrogen doping. The bandgap of anatase TiO₂, wurtzite ZnO and cubic ZnTiO₃ were decreased from 3.65 to 3.50 eV, 3.23 to 3.21 eV and 3.91 to 3.80 eV respectively with increase in calcination temperature from 450 °C to 700 °C.

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